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Gimnastika sport turining turlari va tasniflashi.

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Anatatsiya: Gimnastik mashqlarnig turfa xilligi ularning o'ziga xos xususiyatlarining yo'naltirilganligiga qarab, gimnastikaning mustaqil turlariga birlashtiriladi. 1984 yilda o'tgan

Umumittifoq anjumanida quyidagi tasniflash tasdiqlangan: gimnastikaning sog'lomlashtiruvchi,

ta'limni- rivojlantiruvchi va sport turlari.

Kalit so'z: "Gimnastika" atamasining bir nechta talqini mavjud. Kelib chiqishi "gimnos"- grek

so'zidan- yalang'och ma'nosini anglatadi (qadimiy greklar jismoniy mashqlarni yalang'och bajaranganlar). Katta ensiklopediyaning birinchi nashrida ushbu so'zning etimologiyasi "gimnazo"- mashq bajarish grek so'zi bilan bog'liq. Uchinchi nashrida esa, ushbu so'z qo'shimcha talqinga ega bo'ladi: mashq qildiraman, shug'ullantiraman.

Gimnastik mashqlarnig turfa xilligi ularning o'ziga xos xususiyatlarining yo'naltirilganligiga qarab, gimnastikaning mustaqil turlariga birlashtiriladi. 1984 yilda o'tgan Umumittifoq anjumanida quyidagi tasniflash tasdiqlangan: gimnastikaning sog'lomlashtiruvchi, ta'limni- rivojlantiruvchi va sport turlari.

Gimnastikaning sog'lomlashtiruvchi turlarida ertalabki gigienik gimnastikasi va kirish gimnastikasi shakllarida, ishlab chiqarishda va ta'lim muassasalarida jismoniy madaniyat daqiqalari shaklida mashqlarni bajarish nazarda tutilgan. Bu qatorga davolash va ritmik gimnastika ham kiritilgan. Ularning asosiy maqsadi inson sog'ligini mustahkamlashdan, mehnatda uning jismoniy va aqliy ishga layoqatligini yuqori darajada saqlab turishdan iborat, mehnat va jamoatchilik faoliyatida faolligini oshirish.

Gigienik gimnastika- sog'likni saqlash va mustahkamlash uchun, jismoniy va aqliy faolligini yuqori darajada saqlash uchun, qattiq jismoniy, aqliy va hissiyotli zo'riqishdan, uzoq muddatli **adinamiya**dan so'ng dam olish uchun qo'llaniladi. Mashg'ulotlar individual va gurux shakllarida bolalar bog'chalarining tarbiyalanuvchilari, maktab o'quvchilari, o'rta maxsus va oliy ta'lim muassasalarinig talabalari bilan, hamda sog'lomlashtiruvchi oromgohlar , sanatoriyalar va harbiy qismlar askarlari bilan o'tkaziladi. Gigienik gimnastika majmuiga yurish va yugurish,

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umumrivojlantiruvchi va amaliy mashqlar kiritilgan. Mashqlar majmui chuqur nafas olish va mushaklarni susaytirish mashqlari bilan yakunlanadi. Mashqlardan keyin havo, suv, quyosh muolajalari o'tkaziladi. Mashqlar va yuklama me'yorlari shug'ullanuvchilarning yoshi, jinsi, sog'ligining ahvoli, jismoniy tayyorgarlik darajasi va boshqa xususiyatlariga qarab belgilanadi.

Gigienik gimnastika kunning har qanday vaqtida o'tkazilishi mumkin: ertalab-kun tartibiga yanada tezroq kirishi uchun, kunduzi- to'plangan charchoqni chiqarish uchun. Uyqudan oldin mushaklarning asosiy guruxlarini zo'riqtirish va keyinchalik susaytirish bilan chuqur nafas olib, chuqur uyquga, kun bo'yi sarflagan kuchini qayta tiklashga, o'tgan kun uchun shukronalik fikrlari va kelajakda muvafaqiyatlarga umid qilishga psixik tayyorgarlik qilish shaklidagi mashqlar juda foydalidir. Harbiylar gimnastikaning ushbu turini kechki uyqudan so'ng kun tartibiga tezroq kirish, jismoniy tayyorgarlikni oshirish va xarbiylarni chiniqtirish uchun ertalab o'tkazadilar.

Kirish gimnastikasi- shug'ullanuvchilarnig o'quv yoki mehnat faoliyatiga tezroq kirishiga yo'naltirilgan. Tashkil etish shakli bo'yicha maktabda "darslardan oldin gimnastika" va ishlab chiqarishda "ishdan oldin" tashkil etiladi. Bu yerda kasbiy harakatlanish harakatlariga yaqin bo'lgan, harakatlar tuzilishi bo'yicha quvvatlovchi va **sensorik** ta'minlovchi mashqlar qo'llaniladi. Mashqlar bajarish jarayonida faol va yuqori ishlab chiqarish va o'quv faoliyatiga yo'naltirilgan fiziologik va psixologik tayyorgarlikga erishiladi. Mashqlarni bajarish vaqti 5-10 daqiqa.

Jismoniy madaniyat daqiqasi, butun o'quv yoki ish kuni davomida jismoniy va aqliy layoqatligini yuqori darajada saqlash uchun, qaddi-qomat buzilishlarini oldini olish uchun jismoniy charchoqni chiqarish uchun qo'llaniladi. U dars yoki ish vaqtida charchoq alomatlarini paydo bo'lganida o'tkaziladi (diqqatning pasayishi, holsizlik va h.). Mashqlar majmui 5-10 mashqdan iborat bo'lishi va 2-5 daqiqa bajarilishi mumkin.

Davolash gimnastikasi - davolash jismoniy madaniyatning asosi (DJM). U jarohat olingandan, kasallikdan, jarohlik operasiyadan va h. keyin organizmning vaqtinchalik yo'qotgan alohida funksiyalarini tiklashga ko'maklashadi. Turli xil kasalliklarda boshqa davolash vositalari bilan majmuida qo'llaniladi. Ayniqsa u tayanch-harakatlanish tizimini davolashda juda samarali. Maktab o'quvchilari uchun davolash gimnastika majmui jismoniy madaniyat o'qituvchisi va tibbiyot xodimi bilan birga, ularning sog'ligida individual chetlanishlarga qarab tuziladi. Davolash muassasalarida mashqlar bemorning individual xususiyatlari va kasallikning xarakterini inobatga olgan holda saralab belgilanadi. Mashqlar majmuiga me'yorlashtirilgan yurish, yugurish, saf tayyorgarligi va anjomlar bilan va anjomlarsiz

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umumrivojlantiruvchi mashqlar kiritiladi: tayoq, gantel, espander, koptok, sakramachoq, gimnastik devorchada va o'tirg'ichda mashqlar va b. Mashg'ulotlarning asosiy shakli bu dars yoki 30-60 daqiqalik muolaja. Zamonaviy bosqichda davolash jismoniy madaniyatning turlariga sog'lomlashtiruvchi gimnastikaning noan'anaviy turlari kiritilgan: korreksion, dam olish, tiklash, nafas olish, bo'g'inlar va h.

Ritmik gimnastika- sog'lomlashtiruvchi gimnastikaning turlaridan biri deb hisoblanadi. Mashqlar majmui umumrivojlantiruvchi mashqlardan, badiiy gimnastika va xoreografiya elementlaridan, yurish yugurish va sakrash usullashtirilgan shakllaridan va boshqa bajarish texnikasi bo'yicha murakkab bo'lmagan mashqlardan tashkil topadi. Ritmik gimnastikaning muhim elementlaridan biri bu musiqali kuzatuv. Ushbu vositalar yordamida organizmga beriladigan fiziologik yuklamaning miqdorini belgilash, shug'ullanuvchilarni psixologik holatini boshqarish, ularning mashg'ulotda faolligini oshirish mumkin. Ritmik gimnastikada bir-biridan mazmuni va dars tuzilish bo'yicha farqlanadigan yetarlicha turlarini ajratish mumkin. Ritmik gimnastikaning sog'lomlashtiruvchi yo'nalishlariga quyidagilarni kiritish mumkin: klassik aerobika, tayanch bosqichlarni qo'llaydigan gimnastika, raqs gimnastikasi, u yerda turli raqs usullari va yo'nalishlari qo'llaniladi (salsa, rok, disko, fank, xip-xop); predmetlar va anjomlarni qo'llaydigan aerobika (step, slayd, fitbol, va b.). Ritmik gimnastikaning sog'lomlashtiruvchi turlarining o'ziga xos qirralaridan biri bu mashg'ulotda aerobik qismning mavjudligi, uning davomida ma'lum me'yorda kardiorespirator (yurak tomir va nafas olish tizimi) tizimning faoliyati mustahkamlanadi, bu esa, o'z navbatida sog'lomlashtirish effektini beradi.

Oxirgi vaqtda ommaviy sog'lomlashtirish harakatida bir qator yangi, noan'anaviy harakatlanish faolligining turlari paydo bo'lgan.

Stretching (holatlar gimnastikasi)- ma'lum bir mushaklar guruxlari va bo'g'inlar harakatlanishini ko'paytirish uchun eng yaxshi sharoitlarni ta'minlovchi holatlar majmuini o'ziga qamrab olgan. **Kallanetika-** bu statik mashqlar gimnastikasi. Sog'lomlashtirish gimnastikasining ushbu turi tizimiga 30 ta mashq kiradi, ularning yuklamasini ma'lum holatni ushlab turish vaqtini cho'zish orqali ko'paytiradilar.

Sheyping-tizim- bu jismoniy mashqlarning ta'siri, ovqatlanishning ma'lum tartibi, shug'ullanuvchilar organizmiga maxsus kompyuter testdan o'tkazishning uyg'unlikda birlashishi. Sheyping- bizning davlatimizda endi rivojlanayotgan tizimlardan biri. Sheyping tizimlarining bir nechta turi mavjud: klassik-sheyping, sheyping-terapiya, xomiladorlar uchun sheyping, sheyping-pro, ozgan tanalar uchun sheyping. Gimnastikaning sharq sog'lomlashtirish tizimlari o'zini qayta tiklash va

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o'zini o'zi saqlash kabi noyob imkoniyatlarga ega bo'lgan inson organizmining zahiralari qo'llash imkonini beradi. Gimnastika majmualari sharq turlarining farqli qirrasini bu ongning etakchiligida erishilgan organizmning ichki va tashqi faoliyatining birligi.

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